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The seventh international scientific
and professional conference

THE RIGHT TO ACCESS (MENTAL) HEALTH CARE

Conference Papers

November 3-4, 2023

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IMPORTANCE OF RESOLUTION OF A CHILD’S DIAGNOSIS FOR PARENTAL MENTAL HEALTH

Abstract: *Parents who receive a diagnosis of a serious medical condition or developmental disability for their child often experience strong emotional reactions such as sadness, disappointment and fear. Resolution of the child’s diagnosis refers to achieving acceptance, putting an end to active grieving, and refocusing on present and future realities. In time some parents are able to come to terms with their child’s chronic condition. Conversely, for unresolved parents, strong negative emotions persist through time. They are more depressed, anxious, and stressed compared to those that are resolved. This paper presents key indicators of resolved vs. unresolved parental status, as well as the relationship between resolution and parental mental health. Parents need support, either in a one-on-one or group setting in order to preserve their mental health and the general well-being of the family. A brief description of the support program created and implemented in Serbia is also provided.*

Keywords: *parents; resolution of diagnosis; mental health; support.*

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1. Introduction

Raising a child brings an abundance of pleasure, joy and gratification for parents. However, learning that a child is afflicted by a serious chronic illness or a developmental disorder represents a highly traumatic experience for most parents. They tend to exhibit numerous intensive negative emotional reactions, such as shock, disbelief, disappointment, anger, fear, but also guilt and shame (Sher-Censor, Shahar-Lahav, 2022). These emotions do not occur in all parents and in the same intensity, but the common thread is that almost all parents experience grief which is observed as a universal parental emotion. Along with coping with difficult emotions, parents face countless other challenges over a long period of time i.e. physical or financial. Parents are often unsure of the prognosis for the child's medical condition and future development; they are burdened with medical procedures and specific requests elicited by the child's illness. Insecurity experienced by parents when facing their child's medical condition can minimize their ability of coping successfully with the situation. Therefore, it is not surprising that studies confirm parental psychological and physical health and general family wellbeing is greatly influenced by the child's medical condition and that parental stress is enhanced by multiple demands placed upon parents (e.g., Cohn et al., 2020, Raina et al., 2005). Due to the prolonged stress and feeling of insecurity with regard to the child's condition, parents of chronically ill children in comparison with parents of healthy children have a higher probability to develop mental health issues. The anxiety they experience is just one of many mental health problems which make it harder for them to adapt to new demands, leading to a poorer quality of life. On the other hand, the new demands derived from the child's condition or specific treatment plans require quick parental adaptation to different situations depending on their child's challenging needs which further burden the parents and require great flexibility within the family system. For that reason, parents experience other unwanted mental health outcomes alongside anxiety, such as depression, guilt, hopelessness, but also indicators of posttraumatic stress disorder (Britner et al., 2003; Duffy, 2011).

Multiple factors can increase or decrease stress in families with a child that is ill. These are associated with individual characteristics of the child, parental characteristics and different forms of available support. Each of these factors can influence family circumstances and a thorough examination of a family indicates that parents need to be understood in a wider context and not only as providers of care for a child with an illness.

The following stand out as key factors associated with intensity of family stress:

1. Parental characteristics (e.g., age, marital status, coping ability);
2. Individual characteristics of a child (e.g., the degree of severity of the medical condition, a child’s temperament, behavioral problems);
3. Social factors (e.g., available social support, quality of marital relations);
4. Economic factors (e.g., socioeconomic status, parental employment status);
5. Cultural context (e.g., acceptance of disability in the community) (Raina et al., 2005).

Although parents of children with different health conditions experience higher levels of stress in comparison with parents of typically healthy children, it is important to point out that many of them adapt successfully to newly developed conditions, with positive family functioning being linked to lower levels of parental anxiety and stress (Nabors et al., 2013). This underlines the importance of recognizing and supporting the observed positive aspects of raising a child with a chronic health condition which include enhanced emotional closeness between family members, personal development, sensitivity towards other people, enjoyment of typical family activities, connecting with other parents in the community, development of amicable relationships with professionals etc. (Green, 2007). Thus, in spite of all the difficulties they experience, many parents find pleasure in their parental role. This point of view allows us to make a shift from the exclusive focus on negative aspects of family life to promoting

family strengths and resources as well as the happiness that can be experienced. This encourages family resilience and desirable aspects of each parent’s mental health (Ćorić, 2022; Naicker, Bury, Hedley, 2023).

Baring in mind the challenges that accompany parenting a child with a chronic health condition, this paper aims to portray the process of parental resolution of their child’s diagnosis, as a key concept in understanding parental emotional adjustment. Resolution is viewed as a protective factor for parental mental health and consequently for parental ability to provide sensitive child care.

2. Parental resolution

Parental reactions to the child’s diagnosis have been a largely debated topic in scientific literature. In contrast to earlier approaches that stressed the linear nature of parental adaptation (from shock, disbelief, and denial to complete parental adaptation), the concept of resolution does not insist on a final stage of absolute parental acceptance of their child’s condition (Barnett et al., 2003). This implies that a parent who has accepted their child’s diagnosis can still occasionally experience sadness and other painful emotions, but the key difference is that these feelings are not overwhelming to a degree to which they used to be at the beginning when the parent was first confronted with information on their child’s diagnosis. Parental resolution is an ongoing process of changing one’s expectations and dealing with emotions that are associated with the reality of parenting a child with a specific diagnosis. Thus, resolution of diagnosis represents a process of acceptance, the end of active grieving, and a refocus on present and future realities (Poslawski, 2014).

Resolution includes cognitive and emotional managing of what was experienced. On a cognitive level, parents must understand the meaning and implications of their child’s diagnosis. All new information concerning the child’s medical condition needs to be incorporated into the parents’ internal mental representations of themselves as parents and of their child. However, some parents find it difficult to accept unwanted information. They tend to deny or minimize the reality of their child’s actual condition or are excessively preoccupied with the past, e.g., investigating why the illness has occurred in their child. As to the emotional level, it is

important for parents to accept and express their emotions, such as disappointment, grief, sadness, anger and guilt so as they could adequately accept their behavior and adjust it to the fact that their child has a serious medical condition. After having experienced intense negative emotions, parents who accept the actual reality of their child’s condition can experience satisfaction, enjoyment and a sense of being connected to their child. This does not mean that they will no longer feel distress with regard to their child’s condition, but their feelings will not be as strong or overwhelming as they used to be at the beginning. It has been demonstrated that parents differ in the degree to which they overcome their initial emotional responses, primarily sadness but also some other painful emotions, and focus on the present. Parents who succeed in this process are categorized as resolved to their child’s diagnosis. Conversely, unresolved parents experience difficulties in emotional adjustment and accepting the reality of the child’s diagnosis, and therefore exhibit pronounced and constant grief (Pianta et al., 1996; Reed et al., 2019). After the initial papers by Marvin and Pianta (Marvin & Pianta, 1996) which focused on the relationship between resolution and the development of secure emotional bonding in a child, many authors continue their studies aimed at fully understanding the concept of resolution. Many authors have confirmed a strong relationship between resolution and emotional bonding of children, and have also pointed to the importance of resolution for mental health and wellbeing of parents (e.g., Di Renzo et al., 2020; Krstić, Mihić, Mihić, 2015; Reed, Osborne, 2019).

Pianta and Marvin (Pianta, Marvin, 1992) have developed a standardized procedure for the assessment of parental resolution which was named *Reaction to Diagnosis Interview*. The aim of this interview is to examine parental resolution of trauma connected to receiving information that their child has a chronic illness or developmental difficulties. It takes approximately 15 minutes to conduct the interview. During the interview parents are asked questions about the period of time when they began noticing that something was not right in their child’s development (“When did you first realize that your child had a problem?”) and how they felt at the time (“What were your feelings at the time of this realization?”). Parents are also requested to share in detail what they experienced when they

received the final diagnosis (“Tell me exactly what happened when you learned of your child’s diagnosis, where were you, who else was there, and what were you thinking and feeling at that moment?”). The key question is aimed at registering how parental feelings change over time (“How have these feelings changed over time?”). Aside from that, parents are asked whether they had and/or have any thoughts about possible causes for their child’s condition. Parental answers depict different personal stories and challenges. Apart from their contribution to understanding parental resolution process, they can serve as a basis for psychotherapeutic interventions and allow professionals to fully grasp the possibilities and difficulties that parents encounter on personal and family level (Orme, 2005).

As already stated, we view resolution as a process of integrating information about the child and the parental emotional reactions they lead to, into parental mental representations of themselves as parents, of their child and their relationship with him/her. Therefore, the aim of the questions asked during the Reaction to diagnosis interview is to determine these parental representations, as well as the patterns characterizing these representations (Marvin, Pianta, 1996; Pianta et al., 1996). The way parents answer these questions portrays their representations of themselves as caregivers, of their child and of their relationship with the child with regard to the experienced trauma. These answers contain elements of resolution or lack of resolution. It is also worth mentioning that, although the interviews classified as resolved can have some elements of lack of resolution and vice versa, it is crucial to observe the dominant pattern in parental answers.

3. Indicators of resolution and lack of resolution

Indicators of resolution include parental acknowledgment of difficulties they experienced upon finding out about their child’s health issues, but also recognizing positive changes that occurred in their feelings towards that particular experience over time. Parents state that they had moved on in life, which includes coping with the condition and focusing on the present and the future. In spite of expressing hope for improvement, they accept their child’s current condition. Resolved parents recognize their child’s difficulties and their role as caregivers in a realistic and objec-

tive manner. Pianta and associates (Pianta et al., 1996) highlighted the specific elements present in parental narratives which are indicative of their resolved status towards the child’s diagnosis:

1. *Recognition of change since the diagnosis.* Parents emphasize the emotional difficulties they experienced at the time of finding out the child’s diagnosis, but point out that these feelings have changed so that they now experience a certain amount of relief. This means that a parent can still occasionally feel sadness or other painful emotions, but these are not as pronounced or as frequent as they used to be at the initial phase of getting to know and understand their child’s condition.
2. *Assertion of moving on in life.* After a period of grief and crisis, the common daily routines and activities are reestablished. Parents declare having moved on with their lives and coped with the information that their child has a chronic medical condition. They manage to focus on the present and turn to the future.
3. *Suspending the search for a reason.* Although parents are interested in the cause for the child’s condition, the active search for answers to that question stops. A parent consciously suspends looking for answers acknowledging that this draws attention away from the present reality.
4. *Accurate representation of the child’s abilities.* Parental description of the child’s abilities is in line with the observations made by professionals. A parent can have high but not unrealistic expectations. There can be some uncertainty concerning the future implications and the prognosis for the child’s condition later in life.
5. *Balanced statements regarding benefits of the experience to the self.* Certain ambivalence towards the experience of raising a child with health issues is acknowledged. Parents can mention what they gained (e.g., “I have become a more patient and more accepting parent.”), but also state the difficulties caused by the child’s condition. A parent is able to focus on the positive as well as on the negative aspects of the parenting experience.

Key elements pointing to the lack of resolution have also been determined and they are mainly associated with pronounced parental grief and sadness. With regard to this, parental attention is not primarily focused on the cognitive and emotional reality linked to the child’s condition, but on distorting reality. Therefore, parents can neither recognize their child’s psychological needs accurately nor bond with him/her. The most important indicators of unresolved parental status include the following:

1. *Cognitive distortions.* Parents exhibit unrealistic beliefs, denial and insisting on the desired reality (to have a “perfect child”, i.e. a child that is psychophysically healthy). Cognitive distortions can be viewed as a search for contradicting evidence with regard to the child’s condition (e.g., looking for a confirmation that the diagnosis was wrong) and a belief that the illness would go away.
2. *Active search for reasons.* The process involves an active search for causes and reasons for the child’s disability. Even when the parents are explicitly told that finding out the exact cause for the child’s condition would not alter the prognosis, parental focus remains on searching for a cause. This draws the parents away from dealing with painful emotions, but also from connecting with their child on a psychological level.
3. *Stuck in the past.* Parental attention is focused on the past instead the present in several ways. One of them pertains to parental sadness remaining an ongoing emotional crisis which can intensify over time as the child gets older. Typically, when talking about past parents use the present tense, discussing it with sorrow and pain “as it was yesterday”. Parents can also be preoccupied with anger over the entire experience they have with their child. Finally, parental perception of themselves as parents can be such that their identity is defined through the trauma of their child’s diagnosis, while simultaneously viewing themselves as helpless.
4. *Cut off from the experience of the diagnosis.* Insisting on not having any recollection of the emotions experienced at the time of diagnosis. They remember events and details accurately, but minimize their

own emotional response (e.g., “Finding out my child’s diagnosis has not upset me or had any importance for me.”).

5. *Confusion and mental disorganization.* Parents’ answers and incoherent and disoriented which makes their story and emotional experience hard to understand. This process involves losing one’s train of thought, experiencing difficulty in finding answers and contradicting oneself (e.g., parent gives extremely positive and extremely negative descriptions of a particular experience in the same sentence). This is an indicator of absence of organized mental strategies for dealing with the diagnosis.

4. Resolution and parental mental health

Studies that investigated the relationship between parental wellbeing and resolution have confirmed that parents with unresolved status reported poorer mental and physical health than parents with resolved status and that their health had deteriorated over the first year following the diagnosis (Lord, Ungerer, Wastell, 2008; Reed, Osborne, 2019). Unresolved parents reported suffering from higher parenting stress in comparison to resolved parents, as well as more social strain (Dolev et al., 2016; Krstić, Mihić, Mihić, 2015; Grogan et al., 2023). They also exhibited lower parenting morale, and lower sense of coherence (comprehensibility, manageability, and meaningfulness in life), than parents with resolved status (Goldberg, 2015; Sealy, McMahon, Sweller, 2023). A confirmation of the importance of resolution for parental wellbeing was also obtained from a study which found a more significant increase in parental efficiency in parents who managed to come to terms with their child’s diagnosis after an initial period of unresolved status (Poslawsky et al., 2014). It was also established that grief brought on by learning the child’s diagnosis, and the onset of depression in mothers can have a negative impact on maternal coping and achieving resolution (Kearney et al., 2011). Multiple studies have confirmed that parents who are unresolved towards their child’s diagnosis have higher levels of depression in comparison to those who are resolved (e.g. Dolev et al., 2016; Krstić, Mihić, Mihić, 2015). However, a small number of studies found no significant association between resolution and parents’ psychological distress or symptoms of depression (Popp

et al., 2014; Poslawsky et al., 2014) which implies that the link between resolution and mental health is a complex one and that several factors can pose a potential risk for parental resolution, and mental health in general. Also, the nature of this relationship is difficult to establish, i.e. whether parental wellbeing is a contributing factor or the outcome of resolution, and this is being widely debated in longitudinal studies (Yaari et al., 2017; Reed, Osborne, 2019). Nevertheless, a review of literature indicates that the majority of studies show resolved parental status to be significantly associated with better parental wellbeing overall (Sher Censor & Shahar-Lahav, 2022).

As to the family functioning, unresolved parents reported poorer marital relationships (Leblond et al., 2019). There are numerous risk factors in the family environment that hamper parental resolution including the accumulation of demands in childcare, which are due to his/her condition, that need fulfilling (Krstić, Mihić, Mihić, 2015). Studies examining general coping styles in the face of stressors found no significant links between coping and resolution, although the specific coping style of escape-avoidance was shown to be more prevalent in unresolved parents (Krstić, Mihić, Oros, 2017; Lord, Ungerer, Wastell, 2008).

Also, lower parental educational level was singled out as one of the risk factors for not achieving resolution (Krstić et al., 2016).

Even though in this paper we are primarily interested in parental mental health and resolution, the indisputable significance of parental state of mind for the child’s wellbeing is also worth mentioning. Studies conducted on parents of children with different types of health conditions have shown lack of resolution to have negative effects on parental behavior and the parent-child relationship. Accordingly, unresolved mothers were found to be less sensitive towards their child compared to mothers with resolved status, and the children of parents with unresolved status were more likely to form insecure attachments than the children of parents whose were resolved (e.g., Di Renzo et al., 2020; Sher-Censor et al., 2017).

5. Support for parental resolution

Although parents are under significant strain and stress, the support aimed directly at them and their mental health is generally absent. The

support is primarily directed at the child while the parent receives it sporadically, only if they seek help on their own initiative from a therapist or psychiatrist for the emotional pressure they are under. This kind of attitude is mainly derived from the dominant medical model of illness which supports the patients' right to be cared for. However, since the parents are not direct patients, the gradual change towards the social model of illness would give a wider context and take into account the needs of all family members (Ivanović, Petrović, 2022; Milićević, 2019).

Since parental resolution of their child's diagnosis has proven to be significant for parental mental health and their relationship with the child, it is important to support the parents in the process of coming to terms with diagnosis upon learning that there are problems in the child's developmental or health status. Professionals working with children can be instrumental in facilitating the resolution process, with likely positive effects for both parents and children (Oppenheim et al., 2007).

As the family experience and the need for information change, professionals must be prepared to provide new information, as well as make it easier for parents to redefine their situation since this has proven to be a successful coping strategy. Understanding parental coping and steering them towards more adaptive coping strategies also has an effect on strengthening quality interaction between parents and counselors/therapists (Barak-Levy, Paryente, 2023; Krstić, Oros, 2012).

There are several ways of working with parents, and these can be carried out individually or in group sessions. Commonly, in the beginning phases of coming to terms with the diagnosis, individual meetings with parents are recommended. The support does not necessarily come from psychologists or therapist, but it can also come from other professionals treating the child, such as doctors, special education and rehabilitation professionals and therapists of various profiles. Clear information and guidance as to what they should do to encourage their child's development helps parents a great deal. They also find it very important that professionals show empathy towards them so that they would know they hadn't been left to fend for themselves. Help from institutions and support services has been particularly valuable to families whose child has a more serious form of illness or developmental delay (Krstić, Oros, 2012; Krstić, Mihić, Oros,

2017). Moreover, the help obtained from informal sources, from relatives, friends and other persons from their social surrounding can have great benefits for parents. Resolved parents maintain that they enjoy the support of their extended family (Leblond et al., 2019).

Taking into account all the difficulties parents are facing, professionals are increasingly aware of the need to create adequate, goal driven psychotherapeutic interventions. It is very important to recognize parental feelings and thoughts towards the child's condition so that the support could be directed at parents of children with chronic health conditions, especially unresolved parents (Krstić et al., 2013). Therefore, accepting parental grief and other painful emotions is an important aspect of psychotherapy and counseling. Parents need to be allowed to express their feelings and to be told that they are normal and expected. Support in the early stages of facing the information that their child has developmental difficulties or a serious chronic illness means a great deal to parents, particularly when they find it hard to adapt to this information. It is important to speak openly with parents during the initial period of adaptation, but also at all later stages. Some parents minimize the need for support and insist on not having negative experiences or unpleasant emotions regarding their child's condition. However, the minimizing attitude is not appropriate because it interferes with the parental ability to sensitively interpret and respond to their child's needs (Krstić et al., 2021; Steinberg, Pianta, 2006). Parents need to be encouraged to explore different emotions that they experience towards their child and allowed to express extreme or contradictory feelings since most parents often feel insecure or frustrated with regard to their child's condition or diagnosis. Parents can insist on asking how the diagnosis and the health complications would affect their child's future as well as that of the entire family, but the professionals can be unable to provide a clear answer especially at their child's young age. Therefore, it is important to understand parental insecurity. They need to be provided with professional support in order to overcome difficulties caused by the uncertainty of their child's future development and possible implications of the child's diagnosis (Krstić, Mihić, Branković, 2021; Krstić et al., 2017).

Apart from working in a one-to-one setting, support groups have also been very helpful. Parents can benefit from meeting with other parents

who have children with health conditions so that they would feel less isolated. Members of parental groups are an important source of information for each other and parents should be encouraged to share their resources with one another (Orme, 2005). Also, in a group parents validate the emotions felt by other parents, compare them to their own experience and benefit from learning useful coping strategies. This allows them to gradually accept the specific circumstances of their life. Although several authors have confirmed the importance this type of interventions would have on supporting parental resolution, so far only two programs of group interventions intended to support resolution have been developed. One of these programs was created and is being continuously applied in Serbia.

The program created by Barnett and associates (Barnett et al., 2003) titled “*Building New Dreams*” is an 8-session program that implements interventions promoting family well-being by focusing on parental emotional, cognitive and behavioral adaptation to their child’s condition. Authors of the program consider eight sessions to be enough to begin a process that would help parents move forward towards a healthier type of adaptation.

At the end of this paper, we will give a brief presentation of the program created and applied in Serbia. The name of the program is “*Our Story*”, and it is intended for parents of children with developmental difficulties or chronic health issues (Krstić, Mihić, Branković, 2021; Krstić et al., 2017). The main goal of the program is aimed at promoting and supporting resolution in order to provide quality care for the child and achieve a state of wellbeing for the entire family. The program “Our story” is a structured psycho-educational program. Psycho-education was chosen as the key method since it is an approach that includes both educational and counseling components. The educational component refers to the exchange of important information with regard to the aim of each session so as to provide the participants with a framework for their personal experiences. The counseling component refers to encouraging each participant to recognize the process they are going through, by means of exchange with other participants. The program is conducted in six thematic sessions, each lasting 90 minutes. It is recommended that the group includes 4-6 partici-

pants which allows plenty of interaction between parents. The sessions follow the parents' life story from getting ready for parenthood, through learning the diagnosis, up to the present moment. The accent is placed on promoting and supporting parental sensitivity and resolution. At the end of each session parents are given handouts in a form of a short essay written in a simple and understandable manner. Their aim is to reiterate key information and processes presented during a session to allow parents to recapitulate their own processes and maintain continuity till the next session. These are the sessions:

Session 1: *Parenting and the development of a care system: How I became a parent*

The session takes the parents back to the beginning of their parenting life story. Parents are instructed to think about how they prepared to be parents and the optimistic expectations they had built. Parents share their personal experiences with other parents and notice that the gradual development of the parenting role is in the function of preparing each parent to provide adequate care for their child.

Session 2: *How I became the parent of my child*

In this session the accent is placed on the fact that the parents are not mentally prepared for parenting a child with a serious health condition. Therefore, learning the diagnosis represents a specific experience for them, one that is often followed by painful emotions such as sadness. The spectrum and the intensity of parental emotions vary and the parents share their experiences with each other.

Session 3: *Travel through experience: How I understood and experienced caring for my child*

This session is aimed at recognizing and describing parental process of adaptation. Key elements of resolution are recognized, such as the development of constructive coping strategies. The main goal is for parents to identify strategies which can help them personally in the process of adaptation.

Session 4: *Change: When and how the change in understanding my role as a parent has occurred*

In this session the accent is placed on the desired change in parental emotions and way of thinking so as to facilitate adaptation and resolution. It is also intended that the parents recognize the effects of these changes on the quality of childcare, but also how the change they experienced has affected their own wellbeing.

Session 5: How I became the parent of my child

This session is aimed at parental sensitivity, as an ability to recognize and understand the child's needs and to react to them in a timely and adequate fashion. The importance of strengthening the support network and preserving parental mental health is also highlighted. This will decrease anxiety and the sense of loneliness, but also facilitate the provision of quality care for the child.

Session 6: Acceptance: How can I become a resolved and sensitive parent to my child

The final session is aimed at accentuating all key processes involved in the process of resolution by means of summarizing the participants' experiences. The attention is turned to rounding up each participant's life story with an emphasis on the present moment, i.e. focusing on the cognitive and emotional acceptance of the child's condition and parental wellbeing.

6. Conclusion

Learning that one's child has a significant medical condition or developmental delay can provoke a spectrum of intense negative emotions in parents. The emotional response of parents to their child's diagnosis has been widely debated by researchers and clinicians. Over time, researchers established the concept of resolution with the child's diagnosis as a process of acceptance and coming to terms with the child's health condition. Resolution implies the integration of parents' emotions and information regarding their child's condition within the parents' mental representations of themselves, their child and their relationship with their child. The resolution process of parents of children who receive a diagnosis of a chronic disease or developmental disability is profoundly important both for the parents and for the children. Studies have established strong associations between parental resolution and better outcomes for children with various

health conditions as well with parental well-being and family adaptation and functioning. Parents who have persistent unresolved feelings about their child`s diagnosis experience considerably higher distress than parents who are more resolved about the diagnosis. The process of coming to terms and being resolved can be a long-term one because parents may need to readjust and come to resolution with each new challenge or new developmental stage of their child. Therefore, professional support offered to parents is not less important than the one provided to the child. It is imperative to raise awareness in professionals working with children with health conditions on the importance of resolution and on the role they can have in supporting parents in the often difficult and painful resolution process. Coming to terms with and being resolved towards the child`s diagnosis should be targeted in prevention and intervention programs in order to facilitate healthy adaptation of parents and strengthen their abilities of coping with the stress within the family.

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